

NOTES

Functions of Bases in Chemical Reactions of Oxohalomolybdates (V)

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Oxohalomolybdates(v) have been the subject of immense interests in recent times. But nothing more than the isolation and study of certain physical properties of some salts has appeared in the literature. During our detail investigations of the chemical reaction of $[\text{MoOX}_5]^{2-}$ (where X = Cl⁻ and Br⁻) ion we have come to know that the ion exhibits many interesting chemical properties and undergoes various changes yielding new products. Obviously, this is the manifestation of Mo-O bonding interaction in the species MoO^{3+} present in oxohalomolybdates(v). Nevertheless, the base, R in $(\text{RH})_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$ as well as X are equally important in deciding the course of the reaction and the type of products.

In our present investigations we have isolated the new compounds α -Picoline (Pic = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$) and Piperidine (Pip = $\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}\text{N}$) salts of oxopentachloro- and oxopentabromomolybdate(v) ions and have studied their properties. In order to see how the nature of base (i.e. pyridine, α -picoline and piperidine) influences the course of a reaction we have studied two reactions i.e., (i) ethanolysis and (ii) reaction with acetylacetone. In our previous communication¹ we reported that pyridine salts of $[\text{MoOBr}_5]^{2-}$, $[\text{MoOBr}_4]^-$ and $[\text{MoOCl}_5]^{2-}$ ions on ethanolysis (refluxing or prolonged boiling in dehydrated ethanol) yield a copper-red diamagnetic complex $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{X}_4\text{py}_2]$ easily as a result of partial dehydrohalogenation and simultaneous dimerisation. On repeating the same experiment with α -Picoline and Piperidine salts we have noticed that they do not undergo such reactions. It is of interest to mention in this connection that the ammonium, alkalimetal and ethylenediamine salts on ethanolysis precipitate the halides of the bases leaving behind a brown solution containing the hydrolysed species of MoOCl_3 etc. in solution, whereas, in the case² of 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy) and 1,10-phenanthroline(phen) salts, nonelectrolytic paramagnetic reddish pink complex $\text{cis-}[\text{MoOX}_3\text{L}]$ (where L = bipy or phen) is obtained as a result of complete dehydrohalogenation,

Thus, it is seen that the strength of the base and its coordinating capability with the oxo-metal entity MoO^{3+} determines whether dehydrohalogenation will take place or not. We are thus led to generalise broadly from our investigations that, (a) salts of weak bases having high potentiality as a ligand (bipy or phen etc.) on ethanolysis will yield nonelectrolytic

paramagnetic complexes $[\text{MoOX}_3\text{L}^-]$ as a result of complete dehydrohalogenation, (b) salts of stronger bases like alkali metal ions, ammonium, ethylenediamine etc. will throw down the corresponding halides of the bases as precipitate as a result of ethanolysis and (c) in other cases, especially in pyridine salt the dehydrohalogenation is accompanied by dimerisation and the product is diamagnetic $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{X}_4\text{py}_2]$.

In the case of other reaction i.e. with acetylacetone ($\text{acac} = \text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{COCH}_3$), the base R in $(\text{RH})_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$ is again a predominant factor in deciding the nature of products. Thus, the diamagnetic compound³ $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3(\text{acac})_4]$ containing the unit $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3^{4+}$ results with stronger bases. But in our present series of investigations we have noticed that pyridine salts yield altogether a new series of compounds, $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOBr}_3(\text{acac})]^\dagger$ and $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOCl}_3(\text{acac})]$ which on heating to a temperature of 110° – 130° in an inert atmosphere yield the paramagnetic mixed-ligand nonelectrolytic complexes $[\text{MoOX}_2\text{py}(\text{acac})]$ as a result of dehydrohalogenation,

But α -Picoline and Piperidine salts do not undergo this reaction. We have also studied the reactions of 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline salts and have isolated $\text{trans}[\text{MoOX}_3\text{L}]$ which will be reported soon. All these reactions are under detail investigations and a mechanistic interpretation will be reported later on. Analysis and magnetic susceptibility determination were carried out as usual¹. Analytical data are tabulated in table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	Colour	Mo(%)		Halogen(%)		N(%)		Oxidation State	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.		
$(\text{PicH})_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$	Green	20.18	20.09	37.15	37.13	5.55	5.87	5.04	1.51
$(\text{PipH})_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$	Green	21.08	20.87	38.24	38.50	6.25	6.08	4.99	1.81
$(\text{PicH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$	Greenish yellow	14.00	13.71	57.72	57.11	4.20	4.00	5.07	1.65
$(\text{PipH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$	Yellowish brown	13.71	14.05	58.98	58.53	4.09	4.10	5.02	1.50
$(\text{PyH})[\text{MoOCl}_3(\text{acac})]$	Brown	24.13	24.07	27.07	26.70	3.89	3.52	5.01	1.60
$[\text{MoOCl}_2(\text{py})(\text{acac})]$	Greenish gray	26.25	26.50	19.68	19.58	4.11	3.87	4.98	1.80
$[\text{MoOBr}_2(\text{py})(\text{acac})]$	Brownish black	21.12	21.34	45.20	45.54	3.79	3.99	4.99	1.68

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